

Knowing How, Knowing Why, Knowing Whom: Examining the Alignment of the MBA Programs with the Intelligent Career Theory Framework (ICTF)

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ABSTRACT: This study explored the relationship between the Intelligent Career Theory framework (ICTF) and the MBA's Program Educational Objectives (PEO). Employing a self-reported questionnaire survey with 11 MBA graduates from the past five years, the research examined graduates' perceptions of the program's effectiveness in fostering skills and knowledge aligned with the core ICTF components: Knowing Why (Intrinsic motivation and career goals), Knowing How (Knowledge & skills), and Knowing Whom (professional networks & mentors). Pearson's correlation coefficients were utilized to analyze the relationship between these ICTF components and the program's PEOs. The Permutations were employed to deal with the limitations of a small sample. The significant correlation between the ICTF components and PEOs with the relative strength of know-why and weakness of know-whom provide insight into the program's alignment with career intelligence development. Recommendations for curriculum improvement and ongoing program evaluation based on the ICTF framework are presented. This study highlights the value of ICTF as a tool for enhancing MBA programs and empowering graduates for successful careers.

KEYWORDS: Intelligent Career Theory Framework, MBA graduates, Program Educational Objectives, Permutation Correlations.

INTRODUCTION

The number of MBA programs globally is steadily increasing, which has led to the saturation of the job market, with more candidates competing for similar positions (Burt, 2020). In the US alone, the number of MBA degrees awarded annually surpassed 190,000 in recent years, contributing to heightened competition for desirable roles. Accompanying the high cost of MBA programs, there is a rising trend of salary stagnation or slower growth in MBA graduates' compensation packages. The Financial Times Global MBA Rankings data reveal that while average MBA salaries remain high, the increase rate slowed compared to the previous years (Chan et al., 2024).

Many MBA graduates struggle with the relevance of their chosen specialization in a rapidly evolving market. Reports from job portals and recruitment firms indicate that specific MBA specializations, such as finance or general management, encounter stiffer competition and fewer opportunities than emerging fields like data analytics or sustainable business (Journal, 2024). Also, the economic downturn and geopolitical instability affect MBA graduates' career prospects. Insights into globalization from the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and World Bank (WB) reveal that economic trends affect hiring patterns and investment decisions, thus influencing MBA graduates' job opportunities (A Potential Recession During Grad, 2023).

The COVID-19 pandemic is another key point accelerating the adoption of remote work, presenting challenges for MBA graduates accustomed to traditional office environments. Remote work trends and challenges, such as maintaining productivity, collaboration, and work-life balance in a virtual setting, are several work arrangements MBA graduates must adjust (Maximizing MBA Graduate Potential, 2001). Due to the situation, there is a disconnect between the skills MBA graduates possess and those demanded by employers. A talent management firm underlines skill gaps in digital literacy, adaptability, and creativity, which are increasingly valued in today's job market (What Skills Are Employers, n.d.).

Building professional networks is crucial for MBA graduates' career advancement, but they meet challenges in networking, especially in virtual or socially distanced settings (Dobrow & Higgins, 2005). LinkedIn survey on networking habits gave insight into the effectiveness of virtual networking strategies and the effect of reduced in-person interactions (What Are the Most, 2024).

A well-designed and implemented MBA curriculum can address the career development challenges of MBA students within the Intelligence Career Development Theory (ICTF) framework (Marino et al., 2019). A balanced mix of technical and soft skills development within the curriculum to validate that students acquire both the necessary technical knowledge and essential soft skills such as communication, teamwork, and leadership. Comparatively, a career clarity enhancement workshop, coaching session, and self-assessment tool facilitate MBA students to gain a clearer understanding of their career goals, values, and motivations, expanding their intrinsic value capital and self-management skills (Majid et al., 2019). An ICTF integrates leadership development programs within the curriculum to supply MBA students with opportunities to complement their leadership skills, strategic thinking, and decision-making abilities, facilitating early career challenges effectively (Joyner & Mann, 2011).

Coupled with creating networking opportunities, mentorship programs, and industry interactions to establish social-cultural capital through professional experiences, friendship networks, and relationships with industry professionals, upgrading career prospects and professional image (Pandiyan, 2011). Experiential learning offers opportunities such as internships, consulting projects, and case competitions to provide hands-on experience and practical application of theoretical knowledge, bridging the gap between academic learning and real-world career challenges (Awaysheh & Bonfiglio, 2017).

The MBA program's Program Educational Objectives (PEO) are critical in promoting the ICTF to enhance the knowledge base (know-how). PEO focuses on strengthening graduates' understanding of core business concepts and principles. ICTF's solid knowledge base is essential for adaptive career planning and decision-making. In skill development (know-why), PEO regarded developing business-related skills such as communication, leadership, and negotiation. These skills align with ICTF and consider adaptability, learning agility, and skill diversification (Hwang et al., 2011). For networking opportunities (know-whom), PEOs encourage expanding professional networks through connections with classmates, faculty, and industry professionals. Networking is a critical component of the ICTF, facilitating career exploration and access to diverse opportunities (Marino et al., 2019).

This study intends to determine a significant relationship between the indicators of the ICTF, know-who, know-why, and know-whom, and the MBA PEO among MBA graduates for the past five years. The ICTF Dr. Michael B. Arthur and his colleagues offer a comprehensive framework for understanding career development in a rapidly changing business environment (Arthur et al., 2005). By applying the principles of ICTF to the outcome of the MBA curriculum, the study gives insight into their career development challenges.

RELATED LITERATURE

In a rapidly evolving business environment, MBA (Master of Business Administration) degrees have become increasingly common for professionals looking to advance their careers and expand their skills but may need to do more to indicate success, such as pay rates and job titles fully capture the multifaceted nature of career advancement (Modestino et al., 2019). Measuring career development using a tracer study approach sheds light on all aspects of career success beyond traditional measures (Savickas, 1994). Intelligent Career Theory includes several characteristics: flexibility, continuous learning, and strategic business management (Arthur et al., 2005). Unlike traditional career success indicators, which primarily focus on tangible outcomes such as salary growth or rank promotion, Intelligent Career level assessments provide a nuanced understanding of individuals' ability to traverse career complexity, anticipate industry trends, and take advantage of emerging opportunities (Crowley-Henry Almeida, Bertone & Gunasekara, 2023).

The Intelligent Career Framework allows researchers to delve into graduates' experiences, perspectives, and decision-making processes related to their career advancement. The actual pinnacle of characteristics for MBA graduates is to seek strategies for more excellent opportunities and understand the factors affecting graduate intelligence career levels (Arthur et al., 2005). Employers gather input from industry professionals, employers, and career consultants interacting with MBA graduates in various capacities, providing valuable external validation of graduates' Intelligent Careers and insights advantageous regarding skills and attributes valued in the workplace. Rae and Blenker (2024) surveyed professionals from various industries to identify critical determinants of entrepreneurial intelligence and assess their relevance to MBA graduates. Combining employee insights with data that gain insight into the underlying skills, attitudes, and behaviors concluded that they are relevant to employment issues in the real world (McNamara & McCollum, 2004).

Individuals face increasing career challenges in an era of change and a dynamic workplace. The Intelligent Career Framework provides a valuable lens through which to understand and manage career dynamics in this complex environment (Hunter, 2016). Developed by scholars such as Susan Parker and Michael Arthur, the framework emphasizes cultivating three critical components of an Intelligent Career: knowing why, knowing how, and knowing who (Gunz & Peiperl, 2007).

"Knowing why" means understanding one's career goals, motivations, and aspirations. Examining the Intelligent Career level displays explicit career goals and how they align with their actions and decisions. The importance of intrinsic motivation in providing career success and satisfaction among MBA graduates explores their career aspirations and the factors that influence their career choices, demonstrated motivations, and the extent to which they align with their work styles (Ng et al., 2016). They gain insight into the role of intrinsic motivations in shaping work behaviors. This dimension focuses on an individual's motivations, values, and aspirations, including knowing self, understanding strengths and weaknesses, clearly envisioning the desired career path, aligning personal values with career choices, and finding meaningful work for a larger purpose (Eva & Regehr, 2007).

"Knowing how" includes practical skills, competencies, and capabilities needed to meet business challenges and achieve success. Through quantitative measures such as performance appraisal, competency appraisal, self-assessment, etc., investigate acquiring and implementing knowledge solutions and strategic thinking (Parker et al., 2009). The framework determines how completed skills align with the job's requirements by linking different levels to objective performance outcomes such as career advancement and leadership roles (Hopkins et al., 2006). Furthermore, case studies, focus groups, and other qualitative real-world methods provide insights into graduates' experiences applying acquired knowledge to business challenges. This aspect identifies knowledge and skills that are necessary for success in a variety of roles and situations. This includes technical skills, problem-solving skills, and ongoing learning to adapt to changing business requirements. Acquiring and adapting to diverse skill sets prepares individuals to navigate unexpected career changes and find new opportunities (Pinnington, 2011).

"Knowing who" refers to building and using professional relationships, networks, and social capital to advance one's career. The tracer study examines the impact of social capital on graduates' career trajectories by examining their networking behaviors, mentoring experiences, and business relationships. The role of mentoring relationships with emphasis on career development and ease of achievement among MBA graduates typically use mixed methods to examine graduate students' communication styles, the quality of their professional relationships, and the impact of mentoring on career outcomes (Dobrow & Higgins, 2005), through measures such as communication size and diversity with insights attitudes towards the networking experiences of graduates. This dimension emphasizes the importance of relationships and connections to gain a fuller understanding of the role of social capital in managing entrepreneurial behavior (Rodriguez, 2021). Building strong relationships with mentors, colleagues, and industry professionals provides valuable guidance, opportunities, and support throughout their careers. Active corporate engagement, developing strategic relationships, and using networks open doors for growth and cooperation (Sherif et al., 2020).

The Intelligent Career Framework emphasizes the interplay between these three dimensions by guiding skill development to achieve personal goals. Knowing Why informs Knowing How. Similarly, Knowing Who complements Knowing Why by providing individuals with different perspectives and Knowing How by providing learning opportunities and resources (Hunter, 2016). This strategy also emphasizes the dynamic nature of career development. As individuals develop, they acquire motivations, skills, and connections, requiring constant adjustment and reinvestment in every aspect (Guo et al., 2022).

The Intelligent Career Framework works at different stages of a person's career journey. It guides career exploration, helping individuals discover and match their passions with possible career paths. Skill development focuses on acquiring relevant skills and knowledge based on individual aspirations and career development (Arthur et al., 2002). Networking encourages relationship building and provides opportunities to support career growth. In the case of business change, existing skills and networks are used to manage changes in projects, processes, or organizations (Parker et al., 2009). By exposing MBA graduates to the interconnections and dynamics of these concepts, the Intelligent Career Framework empowers them to take ownership of their professional growth and manage today's environment with purpose, flexibility, and resilience (Dickmann & Doherty, 2010).

MBA degrees have become increasingly common in a competitive business environment as professionals seek to enhance their career prospects and develop leadership skills. However, in an effective MBA program, there is an increasing interest in determining successful and satisfied graduates (Wang & O'Reilly III, 2010). The purpose of this study is to investigate the importance of measuring

the relationship between the educational objectives of the MBA program and the intelligent careers of MBA graduates through a comprehensive tracer study analysis.

MBA programs typically outline specific educational objectives aimed at equipping students with the knowledge, skills, and competencies needed to succeed in the world of work. These objectives typically include developing critical thinking and leadership qualities, enhancing research skills, and enhancing ethical decision-making (Davidson & Burke, 2011). However, the extent to which these objectives align with the evolving requirements and dynamics of business requires investigation

Intelligent Career Theory (ICT) provides a conceptual framework for understanding career development in the modern context. It emphasizes the importance of flexibility, agility, and ongoing learning in navigating career paths (Arthur et al., 2005). According to the Intelligent Career Framework, knowledgeable individuals are better equipped to manage career change, take advantage of opportunities, and achieve long-term success.

Analyzing correlations between MBA programs' educational goals and graduates' career levels allows researchers to evaluate the congruence between program outcomes and career outcomes. Areas of strength are identified by identifying the relationship between specific educational interventions and performance indicators such as job advancement, promotion, and wage growth (Dreher & Ryan, 2002). The findings of the correlation study convey information aimed at ensuring that MBA programs remain relevant and responsive to the needs of students and employers (Tan & Ko, 2019). By identifying the mismatch between educational objectives and job outcomes, program administrators can implement targeted interventions such as academic reforms, experiential learning opportunities, and employment-implemented improvement programs to align system deliverables with business requirements better.

METHOD

This study examined the relationship between the Intelligent Career Theory Framework (ICTF) and the MBA program's Program Educational Objectives (PEO) using the quantitative research design in the form of a self-reported questionnaire survey. This study's target population comprised all MBA program graduates over the past five years (2019-2023). The accessible population included alumni with valid Alumni Affairs Office file contact information. A purposive sampling strategy was employed, targeting a sample of 11 graduates for a manageable workload for data analysis while maintaining an acceptable level of representativeness. The study achieved a diverse sample regarding the number of years graduated and the industry sector to promote the generalizability of findings. However, limitations exist due to the small sample size.

A small sample size of 11 in a correlational study poses limitations but still holds value. Though larger samples are ideal for generalizability (Cohen, 2016), smaller studies are relevant for fewer MBA graduates. Correlational research, instead of studies aiming for causal relationships (Thomann & Maggetti, 2020), benefits from a qualitative depth over sheer numbers. Creswell (2014) highlights the strengths of purposeful sampling, where 11 well-chosen MBA graduates provide rich data representing the key demographics relevant to the research questions. While acknowledging the limitations in generalizability due to its small size, the study focuses on specific population studies. It contributes valuable insights for future research with larger samples on specific population studies and valuable understanding for future research with larger samples that test for broader applicability (Haesebrouck & Thomann, 2021).

A self-reported questionnaire was developed based on the ICTF and the MBA PEOs and divided into three. The demographics section collected basic information about the participants, the year they graduated, and their current industry sector. The ICTF section employed a series of Likert-scale questions to evaluate participants' perception of the program's effectiveness in developing their skills and knowledge aligned with the three core of ICTF elements: knowing how (knowledge & skills); knowing why (intrinsic motivation & career) and knowing whom (professional networks & mentors). Similarly, the last section, PEO, intends to capture a self-reported assessment of the program's effectiveness in attaining its stated educational objectives. The instrument underwent pilot testing with a small sample of non-MBA graduates to ensure the clarity and comprehensiveness of the questionnaire.

The instrument was posted from February 4 to March 8, 2024, on the Official Social Media for the Business Cluster of the Professional Schools alumni. MBA graduates for the past five years were invited to participate. The instrument contained an informed consent form outlining the study's objective, participant anonymity, and data usage procedures.

Descriptive statistics summarized the participants' demographic information. For the ICTF and PEO sections, internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, and Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to explore the relationship between ICTF and PEOs. An alpha level of 0.05 was used to determine statistical significance. Permutation was used to address the limitations of a small sample size and to deal with non-parametric situations (Berry et al., 2011). Equally, permutations provide robust results even with small sample sizes, as they do not depend on assumptions about the underlying data distribution. Shuffling and permuting the data allow for a more accurate estimation of the correlation coefficient, even with the limited data points mitigating the impact of a small sample size. By the same effect, the permutation test reduces the risk of Type I errors, particularly in situations with a small sampling size (LaFleur & Greevy, 2009). Moreover, permutation tests offer flexibility in analyzing correlations, specifically in situations with a small sample size (Yu & Hutson, 2024).

Finally, Cohen's *d* effect size was used to quantify the magnitude of differences between two groups of PEO and ICTF components, specifically when dealing with a small sample size. In the context of correlation analysis, Cohen's *d* furnishes insight into the strengths of the relationship between variables, accounting for the variability within the data (Lovakov & Agadullina, 2021). In case the sample size is small, traditional statistical tests lack sufficient power to detect meaningful effects, making effect size measures such as Cohen's especially useful (Aarts et al., 2014). In addition to statistical significance, by considering the effect size, researchers can better interpret the practical significance of the findings, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between the PEO and the ICTF components (Tomczak & Tomczak, 2014).

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Tracer research tracks the career trajectories of program graduates over time and assesses the outcomes of their education and training (Crowley-Henry, Almeida, Bertone & Gunasekara, 2023). Collecting data on the Tracer study provides valuable insight into the long-term impact of MBA programs on graduates' career development by including measures of intelligent career status. The Tracer study comprehensively assesses graduates' ability to succeed in unpredictable job markets (Baruch & Peiperl, 2000).

Incorporating Intelligent Career-level measures into tracer studies enables researchers to conduct detailed analyses of MBA program outcomes. Quantitative indicators such as salary increases or promotions and qualitative factors such as flexibility, career attitudes (Hay & Hodgkinson, 2006), and commitment to lifelong learning (Kamarudin et al., 2018, June) are examined, and researchers gain a deeper understanding of graduates' overall career readiness and resilience (Marinova, 2017).

Findings from measuring MBA graduates' occupational status can inform strategic planning strategies to increase the curriculum's effectiveness and efficacy (Laud & Johnson, 2013). Program administrators can tailor educational interventions, experiential learning opportunities, and career development resources to better align with industry requirements and emerging trends by identifying areas where graduates excel or struggle with intelligent work habits.

In Table 1, the MBA graduate's response was generally positive self-perceptions about the program's effectiveness in preparing them for their future career. The mean scores across all items ranged from possessing the high practical skills necessary to excel in the chosen field ($M = 4.20$, $S.D. = 0.40$) to a very high level of confidence in the ability to apply theoretical knowledge to real-world business scenarios in actively seeking out opportunities to enhance professional confidence and MBA education furnishing the necessary know-how to navigate complex business environments ($M = 4.30$; $S.D. = 0.46$). These findings align with the Intelligent Career Theory Framework (ICTF), highlighting the significance of theoretical knowledge and practical skill development for career success. The high rating for applying knowledge to real-world scenarios and actively seeking professional development suggests that the program advances graduates' ability to learn and adapt within dynamic work environments, a key concept of ICTF. However, consistency in decision-making regarding the balance between financial sustainability and welfare is critical for immediate career success (Sullivan & Baruch, 2009).

Table 1. Level of ICTF Components among MBA Graduates

Knowing How	Mean	S.D.	D.E.
1. Confidence in applying theoretical knowledge to real-world business scenarios.	4.30	0.46	Very High
2. Possess the practical skills necessary to excel in chosen field.	4.20	0.40	High
3. Actively seek out opportunities to enhance professional competencies.	4.30	0.46	Very High
4. MBA education furnishes the necessary know-how to navigate complex business environments.	4.30	0.46	Very High
Mean	4.28	0.44	Very High
Knowing Why			
5. Clear understanding of career goals and aspirations.	4.30	0.46	Very High
6. Regularly reflect on the reasons behind career choices.	4.20	0.60	High
7. Feel confident in ability to articulate the rationale behind career decisions.	4.20	0.60	High
8. Prioritize aligning career path with personal values and beliefs.	4.50	0.50	Very High
Mean	4.30	0.54	Very High
Knowing Whom			
9. Actively network with professionals in the industry to expand career opportunities.	4.30	0.46	Very High
10. Strong professional support network for career advice and guidance.	4.20	0.60	High
11. Aware of influential individuals within the industry to learn from.	4.20	0.75	High
12. Actively seek out mentors to help navigate career path.	4.40	0.49	Very High
Mean	4.28	0.57	Very High
Overall Mean	4.28	0.52	Very High

4.21- 5.00 very high; 3.41 - 4.20 high; 2.61- 3.40 neutral; 1.81 - 2.60 low; 1.00- 1.80 very low

Examining graduates’ replies through the lens of ICTF reveals encouraging results regarding career clarity. The mean score across statements on “Knowing Why” expresses high in regularly reflecting on the reason behind career choices and feeling confident in articulating the rationale behind career decisions (M = 4.20; S.D. = 0.70). In like manner, a very high rating in aligning career path with personal value belief (M = 4.50; S.D. = 0.50). These ratings claim that graduates strongly understood their career goals and aspirations and prioritized aligning their career paths with personal values. The response aligns with a core principle of ICTF, which focuses on the importance of self-awareness and intrinsic motivation for career success (Sullivan & Baruch, 2009). A slightly lower score for self-reflection and articulating career rationale than goal clarity and value alignment implies areas for potential improvement.

Regarding the MBA graduate’s engagement with professional networks, a vital element of “Knowing Whom” within ICTF is engaging. MBA graduates are highly rated as having a strong professional support network for career advice and guidance; they are aware of influential individuals within the industry to learn from (M = 4.20; S.D. = 0.60-0.75). In the same way, a very high rating of actively networking with professionals in the industry to expand career opportunities and actively seeking out mentors to help navigate career paths (M = 4.40; S.D. = 0.46-0.49). These responses indicate that they actively built professional networks and sought mentorship crucial for career advancement and access to knowledge (Arthur et al., 2002). While the ratings for awareness of influential individuals and support networks were somewhat lower, the overall trend suggests that graduates valued the importance of social capital in career development.

Although the ICTF focuses primarily on individual career development, it recognizes the importance of the broader organizational context (Sullivan & Baruch, 2009). Examining graduates’ self-perceptions of the MBA program's effectiveness in preparing them for this setting presents positive results, particularly regarding leadership and ethical decision-making, displayed in Table 2 below. The mean (M = 4.55, S.D. = 0.50) conveys a high level of developing excellence in leadership and management, signifying that graduates felt well-equipped to lead and manage teams using effective human relations and practices. This aligns with ICTF’s focus on the interaction between individual career development and the need to contribute effectively within organizational structures (Sullivan & Baruch, 2009). The very high-level rating (M = 4.36, S.D. = 0.64) on using quantitative analysis in decision-making related to ethical business issues conveys that the MBA program promoted critical thinking skills crucial in processing complex ethical dilemmas in today’s business environment (DeFilippi & Arthur, 1994). Though comparatively slightly lower but still rated very high (M = 4.36, S.D. = 0.48) financial sustainability and welfare and (M = 4.27, S.D. = 0.62) understanding global business issues, designate areas for potential program improvement, specifically in connection with the increasingly connected global business landscape (Sullivan & Baruch, 2009).

Table 2. Level of PEO Rating among MBA Graduates

MBA Program Educational Objectives (PEO)	Mean	S.D.	D.E.
1. Develop excellence in leadership and management in the business environment through team building and best human relations practices.	4.55	0.50	Very High
2. Demonstrate competency and consistency in decision-making related to the balance between financial sustainability and welfare	4.36	0.48	Very High
3. Display professional understanding of the diverse economic, multicultural, national, and international business global issues.	4.27	0.62	Very High
4. Use both quantitative and qualitative analysis in decision-making to a varied business ethical issue	4.36	0.64	Very High
Mean	4.39	0.56	Very High

Table 3 below conveys the test statistic values for correlations between variables Know-how, Know-why, Know-whom, and Program Educational Objectives (PEO) and relevant information on significance levels derived from permutation distribution. Based on the original data, a strong positive correlation exists between Know-how and Know-why (r = 0.515, p<0.001), Know-why, and PEO (r = 0.556, p<0.001). Similarly, a moderate positive correlation manifests between Know-how and Know-whom (r = 0.156, p<0.01) and Know-why and Know-whom (r = 0.191, p<0.05). The correlation between Know-whom and PEO (r = 0.245, p<0.01) is also significant, with a relatively positive association.

Table 3. Correlation and Test Statistics on the Association Between ICTF and PEO

Data	Variable		Test-Statistic	p-value
Original	Know-how	Know-why	0.515	p<0.001 (sig.)
		Know-whom	0.156	p<0.05 (sig.)
		PEO	0.491	p<0.01 (sig.)
	Know-why	Know-whom	0.191	p<0.05 (sig.)
		PEO	0.556	p<0.001 (sig.)
	Know-whom	PEO	0.245	p<0.01 (sig.)
Permutations	Mean	0.003	Cohen's d effect size*	0.60
Distribution	Std. Dev.	0.086		
	5 th percentile	-0.142		
	95 th percentile	0.142		
Significance	p-value	<0.001 (sig.)		

*0.2 or lower, small effect size; 0.3-0.5, medium effect size; 0.5 or higher, large effect size.

Moreover, the permutations are used to simulate random sampling from the responses. Repeatedly shuffling the data points creates a distribution of correlation coefficient. The various components in the distribution reveal. The mean correlation value across all permutations is approximately 0.003, representing the average correlation expected by chance if there were a true relationship between the variables. Since it is close to zero, it implies that random fluctuations alone did not result in strong correlations. The standard deviation of the correlation values is 0.086, measuring the spread or variability of the correlation coefficients. A larger standard deviation shows greater variability in the simulated correlations. The 5th percentile value is -0.142, and the 95th percentile is 0.142. These represent the range of correlation coefficients expected from random permutations. In other words, about 5% of the simulated correlations fall below -0.142, and 5% fall above 0.142. The bulk of the simulated correlations lie within this range. Based on the p-values and the permutations, it is claimed that there is a significant relationship among the variables.

Moreover, Cohen's d effect size of 0.60 in the correlations between the MBA Program Educational Objectives (PEO) and the three components of the Intelligent Career Theory Framework (ICTF) assessment scores indicate a medium-sized positive relationship expressing a clear though not exceptionally strong association between achieving the PEO goals and performing well on the ICTF. In other words, MBA graduates with a high level of ICTF tend to be closer to achieving the PEOs.

The significant correlations observed between the know-how, know-why, and know-whom constructs, including the MBA Program Educational Objectives (PEO), convey significant implications within the context of the Intelligent Career Theory Framework (ICTF). The strong correlation between the "know-how" construct, which represents practical skills and competencies, and the MBA PEO objectives related to leadership capacity, analytical tools application, and practical problem-solving underscores the effectiveness of the program in equipping graduates with the requisite knowledge and skills to deal with complex business problems. Based on ICTF, MBA graduates display high levels of "know-how" are better to pursue intelligent career strategies, adapt to changing circumstances and advance their careers.

The know-why construct reflects people's understanding of their career motivations and aspirations. The MBA program PEO's significant correlation underlines corporate ethical/social responsibility trend identification in competitiveness, highlighting the program's role in promoting graduates' self-awareness and alignment with their career goals. Within the Intelligent Career Theory Framework, graduates with clarity in their career motivations are more likely to pursue meaningful and fulfilling career paths, contributing to long-term career satisfaction and success.

The emphasis on networking and relationship-building skills is the know-how construct that significantly correlates to the MBA PEO, focusing on leadership and professional development, advocates that the program processes graduates' engagement in professional networks and mentorship opportunities. Regarding ICTF principles, graduates actively cultivate relationships within

their professional circles and are better positioned to access resources, opportunities, and support networks essential for career advancement and resilience.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the potential relationship between the Intelligent Career Theory Framework components (know-how, know-why, and know-whom) and the Program Educational Objectives (PEOs) of the MBA program through self-reported data from graduates of the past five years. A significant correlation exists between the three dimensions of ICTF and the MBA PEOs.

The analysis revealed a significant positive correlation between all three ICTF components and the PEOs; this suggests a strong alignment between the program's curriculum and the development of skills and knowledge aligned with career intelligence. The program effectively equipped graduates with the necessary intrinsic motivation, career clarity, practical skills, professional networks, and mentorship opportunities to direct their careers successfully.

In this case, the program can continue monitoring these relationships through graduate surveys and alumni engagement. However, it could explore opportunities to strengthen specific areas based on ICTF, such as offering more industry-specific electives or enhancing career coaching services.

Though all the components of ICTF are rated very high, the program needs to refine its curriculum based on the know-whom. For instance, a strong correlation between know-how and PEOs indicates that the program delivers strong technical skills. However, a weaker correlation with know-whom (networks) signifies a need for more focus on networking opportunities or career support.

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